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Research Article

**STUDY TO DETERMINE THE GROWING DENTAL
ANOMALIES IN PATIENTS VISITING DENTISTRY
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Abstract:

Background: Growing dental anomalies are variations from the normal, size, shape structure, number and position. Aim of this study was to determine the pattern of developing dental anomalies, compare age and to identify the most common anomaly.

Study Design: This was a descriptive study.

Place and Duration of Study: This study was conducted at the Mayo Hospital Lahore for the period of six months from January 2020 to July 2020.

Materials and Methods: This study was carried out on 350 patients with developmental dental anomalies. Preoperative data were collected through history and clinical examination. Each patient was evaluated for dental anomalies to identify the pattern, most common anomaly and compare the age distribution of anomalies. Statistical analysis included descriptive statistics and χ^2 test. Results were considered significant if $P < 0.05$.

Results: The age range was 8-20 years and maximum number of patients presented in 17-20 years age group (46%). The commonest anomaly was rotation (28%) followed by cusp of Carabelli (14.3%). Rotation was most common in 17-20 years age group. Cusp of Carabelli was most common in 13-16 group and in 8-12 years age group microdontia.

Conclusion: Early detection of anomalies is important to prevent complications.

Key Words: Dental anomaly, Pattern, Hyperdontia, Microdontia.

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INTRODUCTION:

Growing dental anomalies are variations from the normal, size, shape structure, number and position¹. These anomalies are caused by myriad of genetic/ hereditary/ acquired, local as well as systemic factors, influencing either the deciduous or permanent teeth before or after birth^{2,3}.

Globally, the frequency ranges from 1.7% to 5.5%^{4,5}. It is reported that these anomalies variate in number (hyperdontia, hypodontia) predominates than variation in size and shape. Few studies have been done in Pakistan to document dental anomalies in population, which shows varied results ranges from 1.4% to 7.8%.^{6,7,8}. The rationale is to identify the frequency of these anomalies in population adding more data to the literature for future comparisons. This study will also help to generate population characteristics databases which could be used for personal identification purposes like forensic odontology and will also help in the early identification of these anomalies. Once the problem is identified, it will be convenient for healthcare provider to plan comprehensive management for the condition and prevent future complications.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This was a descriptive study conducted at the Mayo Hospital Lahore for the period of six months from January 2020 to July 2020.

Data Collection Procedure: Informed consent was taken from the patient/guardians accordingly. Patients were examined thoroughly clinically for any

developmental dental anomalies, supplemented by detailed history and radiographic study (Periapical and OPG). The data collected were entered in a pre-formed proforma.

Data Analysis: The data were analyzed by applying descriptive statistics and chi-square test and was then calculated by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 16. For age distribution age range, mean \pm SD and percentages of age groups were computed and represented in the form of graph using Microsoft Excel. Similarly, frequencies and percentages were computed for pattern of anomalies, distribution according to age groups. Tabulated and graphic analysis of the data was performed. Data were compared calculating χ^2 and p values. The level of significance was set at $p < 0.05$.

RESULTS:

The age range was 8-20 years, with a mean value 14.5 ± 5.5 years. Maximum number of patients presented in 17-20 years age group (46 %) followed by 13-16 years (39%). The most common anomaly was rotation (28%) followed by cusp of Carabelli (14.3%), while the least common was anodontia (0%) followed by gemination (0.3%). Rest of the detail is given in table 1.

Rotation was most common in 17-20 years age group (n=43). While cusp of Carabelli was common in 13-16 group and in 8-12 years age group microdontia was more prevalent. More detail is given in table 2.

Table No. 1: Distribution of number of developmental dental anomalies and their percentages

S. No	Name of anomalies	No. of anomalies	%tage
1	Microdontia	25	(7%)
2	Macrodontia	2	(0.6%)
3	Gemination	1	(0.3%)
4	Fusion	3	(0.9%)
5	Concrescence	2	(0.6%)
6	Talon cusp	13	(3.7%)
7	Cusp of Carabelli	50	(14.3%)
8	Dens Evaginatus	9	(2.6%)
9	Dens Invaginatus	11	(3.14%)
10	Taurodontism	2	(0.6%)
11	Amelogenesis Imperfecta	14	(4%)
12	Dentinogenesis Imperfecta	5	(1.42%)
13	Anodontia	0	(0%)
14	Hypodontia	34	(9.7%)
15	Oligodontia	3	(0.9%)
16	Hyperdontia	20	(5.7%)
17	Ectopic Eruption	28	(8%)
18	Rotation	98	(28%)
19	Impaction	30	(8.5%)
Total		350	(100%)

Table No.2: Distribution of anomalies according to age groups

S No	Type of anomalies	Age Groups						Total
		8-12		13-16		17-20		
		M	F	M	F	M	F	
1	Microdontia	3(0.8%)	2(0.6%)	4(1.14%)	5(1.42%)	4(1.14%)	7(2%)	25(7%)
2	Macrodontia	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	1(0.3%)	1(0.3%)	2(0.6%)
3	Gemination	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	1(0.3%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	1(0.3%)
4	Fusion	0(0%)	0(0%)	1(0.3%)	1(0.3%)	0(0%)	1(0.3%)	3(0.9%)
5	Concrescence	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	1(0.3%)	1(0.3%)	2(0.6%)
6	Talon cusp	1(0.3%)	1(0.3%)	2(0.6%)	3(0.9%)	3(0.9%)	3(0.9%)	13(3.7%)
7	Cusp of Carabelli	3(0.9%)	4(1.14%)	9(2.6%)	11(3.14%)	10(2.9%)	13(3.7%)	50(14.3%)
8	Dens Evaginatus	0(0%)	1(0.3%)	3(0.9%)	2(0.6%)	1(0.3%)	2(0.6%)	9(2.6%)
9	Dens Invaginatus	0(0%)	0(0%)	2(0.6%)	3(0.9%)	3(0.9%)	3(0.9%)	11(3.14%)
10	Taurodontism	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	1(0.3%)	1(0.3%)	2(0.6%)
11	Amelogenesis Imperfecta	1(0.3%)	2(0.6%)	2(0.6%)	3(0.9%)	3(0.9%)	3(0.9%)	14(4%)
12	Dentinogenesis Imperfecta	0(0%)	1(0.3%)	1(0.3%)	1(0.3%)	1(0.3%)	1(0.3%)	5(1.42%)
13	Anodontia	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)
14	Hypodontia	3(0.9%)	3(0.9%)	6(1.7%)	7(2%)	6(1.7%)	9(2.6%)	34(9.7%)
15	Oligodontia	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	1(0.3%)	1(0.3%)	1(0.3%)	3(0.9%)
16	Hyperdontia	1(0.3%)	2(0.6%)	4(1.14%)	4(1.14%)	4(1.14%)	5(1.42%)	20(5.7%)
17	Ectopic Eruption	2(0.6%)	3(0.9%)	5(1.42%)	6(1.7%)	5(1.42%)	7(2%)	28(8%)
18	Rotation	7(2%)	9(2.6%)	16(4.6%)	23(6.5%)	20(5.7%)	23(6.5%)	98(28%)
19	Impaction	2(0.6%)	3(0.9%)	5(1.42%)	6(1.7%)	6(1.7%)	8(2.3%)	30(8.5%)
Total		23(6.5%)	31(8.8%)	60(17.%)	77(22%)	70(20%)	89(25%)	350(100%)

DISCUSSION:

During routine clinical examination of oral cavity these developmental dental anomalies are noted in clinical practice. A plethora of epidemiological studies, which have been conducted across the globe. Unfortunately, few studies have been conducted in Pakistan about the pattern and prevalence of dental anomalies.

Microdontia: The prevalence ranges from 0.8% to 8.4% in various populations. In this study microdontia was noted in 8.2% of total patients, while Backman et al⁹ had recorded lower percentages in their study.

Macrodontia: Only two patients presented with macrodontia. Macrodontia is much less common than microdontia.^{10,11,12,13}

Macrodontia is noted 0.6% in the present study. Similarly, Patil S¹⁴ gave 0.2% in his study.

Gemination: Gemination is defined an incomplete division of one tooth germ. It has prevalence of 0.1% in permanent dentition.¹⁵ 0.3% of total cases was found in the present study. Similar findings had been given by Guttal KS³(0.28%) and Altug-Atac AT et al¹⁶(0.07%).

Fusion: In the present study 0.6% fusion cases was found. The tooth may be of normal size or larger than normal. The prevalence ranges from 0.02% to 5% based on geographic, racial or genetic factors.^{17,18,19,20} Nearly similar results were given regarding the fusion 0.7% by Kositbowornchai S²¹, 0.23% by Altug-Atac AT et al.

Concrescence: In the present study, only two patients had concrescence constituting 0.6% of all of the dental anomalies. Guttal KS³ had reported 1.4%.

Talon Cusp: During the present study 3.7% talon cusp occurred. Guttal KS³ had reported 4.28%. Overall talon cusp ranges from less than 8% in different populations.^{22,23}

Cusp of Carabelli: The cusp of Carabelli reported in this study is 14.3%. It was seen in 2.17% by Najm MJ et al²⁴ and by Falomo O in Nigeria which was 17.43%.

Dens Evaginatus: In the present study, dens evaginatus comprised 2.6% of the total dental anomalies. Guttal KS et al³ had reported 2.85%. These results are in accordance with results of the

current study. In two successive surveys of over 1,000 Chinese subjects 1.3% and 1.5%, were affected by dens evaginatus.^{25,26} A slightly higher prevalence figure of 4.3% was reported in several Indian studies.^{27,28}

Dens Invaginatus: In the present study the percentages of dens invaginatus was 3.12%. The incidence among several population groups ranged from 0.25 to 5.1%.^{29,30}

Taurodontism: Taurodontism is 0.6% in this study its prevalence has been reported to range between 1.67% and 16%. In study of Guttal KS³, it accounted for 18% and Gupta SK *et al*²² reported 2.49%.

Amelogenesis Imperfecta (AI): It is 3.9% in present study and its prevalence varies from 0.7% to 4% according to the populations studied. The sample of Sener S *et al*²³ included two cases (0.2%), which is comparatively lower than the present study. Najm MJ *et al*²⁴ reported 2.04% and 7.72% in the study of Ezoddini AF *et al*.¹⁰

Dentinogenesis Imperfecta: In this study, DI was found to be 1.4%. 1 case was reported only (0.09%), making it the rarest anomaly.²²

Anodontia: No case of anodontia was noted in the present study.

Hypodontia: Current study showed 9.7%. The recorded prevalence rates of different studies ranges from 0.1% to 11.2%. Tofangchiha M³¹ and coworkers reported a prevalence rate of 9.7%. Figures about hypodontia are in line with the results obtained from studies in Japan³¹ 9.40% and Saudi Arabia³³ 9.41%, while several other studies showed in little bit lower prevalence rates of 6.5%, 7.9%, 7.25%, 6.9%, 7.68% respectively.²¹

Oligodontia: This study showed 0.9% oligodontia. It is relatively rare condition with the prevalence reported to vary from 0.08% to 8%. Altug-Atac AT *et al*¹⁶ had found 0.13%, Backman 1.9%, while Thongudomporn U *et al* a higher percentage (8.1%) in their studies.

Hyperdontia (Supernumerary Teeth): This study recorded 5.5% hyperdontia. The prevalence ranges from 0.3% to 6.5% in various populations.³³ In Caucasians they range from 0.4% to 2.1%; while they are 3.4% for Japanese and 6% for American Blacks.⁴

Ectopic Eruption: This study recorded 7.95%, which is similar to Gupta SK⁴ study. A very high

percentage had been recorded in Pakistan by Abbas Q *et al* with 21.3% of ectopic eruption. This difference is due to the selected orthodontic patients.

Rotation: 28% rotation is noted in this study. Gupta SK⁴ showed that rotations occurred 10.24%. In the present study high prevalence of rotation is due to the fact that 45° and 90° rotations were included.

Impaction: 8.5% impactions were present in this study. Ezoddini *et al*¹⁰ and Thongudomporn and Freer also found a somewhat similar prevalence of respectively 8.3% and 9.9% in non-orthodontic patients.

CONCLUSION:

The most common anomaly was rotation followed by cusp of Carabelli, while the least common was anodontia. Rotation was most common in 17-20 years age group, while cusp of Carabelli was most common in 13-16 and microdontia in 8-12 years. Various anomalies are noted. The presence of such anomalies suggests a complete evaluation of the patient to rule out any syndrome and initiate treatment earlier.

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